

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF INFINITIVE SECONDARY PREDICATES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: In this article, the main features of the English and Uzbek verbs were analyzed. The main differences between Uzbek and English verbs were shown.

Key words: verb, action, state of being, feel, smell, characteristic, situation, literary language, morphological feature, suffix, presence, personal verb, impersonal verb.

The verb is one of the active word groups in all languages. The verb has a wide semantic range, but mainly means a situation that gives the idea of action and action. The learning of the verb word group is inextricably linked to other word groups. The largest group of words is also a verb. Mahmoud Zamakhshari, who was born in Khorezm, wrote several works on linguistics. The work "Muqaddimat-ul Adab" consists of five parts, in the form of nouns, verbs, connectives, noun changes, verb changes. Created. Zamakhshari was the first scientist to group verbs according to their stem. Zamakhshari's place in the study of morphology is incomparable. [1] In the study of the history of the formation of the old Uzbek literary language, one of the important written sources in the work "Tafsir" is used a lot of words of the verb group and in colorful forms. Together with the aspects specific to the old Uzbek language, aspects related to the language of the ancient Turkic times are also shown. The grammatical meanings of personal, tense and mood are expressed in the verb forms mentioned in the work. In this work, full and shortened forms of verbs are used, and detailed information about the word group of verbs is given. [2] Our scientists have noted the work "Muhabbatnoma" which contains all-Turkish features as an example of the old Uzbek written literary language. Indeed, several morphological features are noted in the work. We can know this from the given information about the verb phrase. Some of the verb forms in "Muhabbatnoma" correspond to the old Uzbek language. But the grammatical devices used in some verb forms are characteristic of the language of much earlier times. [3] In the 14th century, there are two other works whose

author is unknown, the first of which is the dictionary "Translator". This dictionary consists of 76 pages and consists of four parts. The first part is devoted to the name, the second part is devoted to the issue of verb tense and action noun, the third part is to the type and declension, and the fourth part is to the use of the word. The first three parts of this work are devoted to morphology, and mainly the verb word family is studied. 8 The second work is the work "At-tuhfa", which also has a very extensive study of the verb family. is given. The categories of verb proportion, indivisibility, person, mood, and tense are covered in detail. This work reflects on the relationship between the unknown, togetherness, addition, and identity. A peculiarity of English verbs is that, in addition to semantic verbs, as in Russian, there are modal and auxiliary verbs, linking verbs, which are usually not translated in any way, but have additional semantic carries a load. One of the unique features of English verbs is that they can be regular or irregular. Irregular verbs differ from regular verbs in that the past tense is formed by adding the suffix. You should use dictionaries, textbooks and a special table available on the Internet to find out what form an irregular verb has in the past or future tense. Another feature of English verbs is the presence of personal and impersonal verbs. Personal verbs act as a predicate in a sentence whenever there is a subject. Impersonal verbs include participles, for example. They rarely act as a predicate, they perform the functions of the rest of the sentence. The distinctive features of English verbs include the way they are formed. There are simple, complex and derived verbs. Simple ones consist only of the root and the ending of the word, for example, hit -hit. Compound verbs are formed by adding the roots of words, for example, to grow -to grow. Derived verbs contain additions and suffixes in addition to the root. Example: dislike -dislike. When learning English, you should devote a lot of time to the verb to be, which is already a characteristic in itself. It performs four functions, most often it plays the role of a semantic verb and a linking verb. Any sentence in English cannot be made without a verb, so to exist exists where there is no semantic verb and there is a compound nominal predicate, for example, I am a student, in Russian " "I am a student" is translated. A verb is a group of words that expresses an action, state or process and has tense, inclination, ratio, perfect, modality and other such grammatical features. Verbs are words that express action. In grammar, the meaning of action is very broad, it includes actions represented by verbs such as to run (yugurmoq), to swim (suzmoq), situations represented by verbs such as to sit down (o'tirmoq), to stand (turmoq), mental changes represented by verbs such as to surprise, to worry, biological phenomena represented by verbs such as to

blossom, to grow, and similar actions and events contains z. In addition to the fact that all of the above have their own specific forms, there is also a common aspect for all of them, that is, they are events that occur in relation to time. A verb is an independent set of words that expresses an action, state or process, that is, an action such as the appearance and change of a certain sign. All such meanings specific to the verb go back to the general meaning of action, which helps to distinguish it from other groups of words. As Yu.S. Maslov pointed out, a verb is a group of words that expresses the grammatical significance of a sign, an action that occurs over time. There are similarities and differences in the mood category of the verb word group in English and Uzbek languages. Indicative mood in Uzbek corresponds to the mood of message, and imperative mood to the mood of command. But English does not have a mood similar to the objective mood in Uzbek, so we can compare the meaning it expresses with Indicative mood (message mood). For example: I want to be a teacher - Men o'qituvchi bo'lmoqchiman. The important thing is that the verb reflects the characteristics of the action that takes place during a certain period of time. These features are manifested in the personal forms of the verb, and therefore the syntactic function of the personal forms of the verb is to be used only as a predicate in the sentence. The word change system of the verb is much richer and more diverse than other word groups. It has not only the synthetic method characteristic of inflectional languages, but also the addition of formants to the root or the analytical method. It should be noted that the verb is the only group of words that has analytical forms. If we pay special attention to the word changing system of verbs, we can see that the suffixed verbs formed by the affixation method are quite rare and the compound verbs formed by the conversion method are quite numerous. Verbs show action (walk, run, write) or a state of being (be, feel, smell, and seem). Verbs have several characteristics: form, tense, person, number, voice, and mood. Some verbs can stand alone in sentence; other verbs are helping verbs. Helping verbs are forms of the words do, be, and have, or the words shall/will, might/must, would/could/should, and can/may. They combine with other verbs to form a complete verb phrase (e.g. was sleeping). Other verbs are called linking verbs. Linking verbs link the subject of a sentence to a description that follows. Linking verbs include forms of the verb be and the verbs seem, appear, become, grow, remain, stay, prove, feel, look, smell, sound, and taste. English also has modal verbs. They are given special attention because these parts of speech differ from other English verbs in a number of features. They are indicators of the characteristic of action and are used together with semantic verbs. For example, a

modal verb must express a request to perform an action. I go to school. I have to go to school. Modal verbs never have the endings –ing, –s and –es. In some cases, modal verbs can be replaced by their equivalents or equivalent universal verbs. Equivalents are usually used instead of modal verbs in the past and future tenses.

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